

Article

Impact of Television on Children

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Abstract

Television is a form of new media and is one of the most important media technologies. This paper focuses on the impact of televised violence, advertisement and sexuality on children. This paper also focuses on the concept of Media Literacy as a useful tool to minimize the harmful effects of TV on the children.

Key Terms

Television, Technology, New Media, Children, Violence, Sexuality, Advertising, Regulation, Media Literacy.

Introduction

Television (hereafter will be referred as TV), an important media technology, continues to dominate the family environment and indoor life. It is thus worthwhile to examine how TV influences the viewers in various ways. Media contents are usually dialogic. TV contents are under polysemy. Hence, with the same programme various interpretations coexist. A relation of cause and effect exists between TV and its viewers. (Tester1994: 57-9). Social and psychological interpretations of TV exist. The message is not always decoded in the way the producer wants. For instance, sub-cultural settings and formations are very important in how

an individual will response to a media message. (Morley and Brundson1999: 126-30). Culture is very important in deciding how media content will be analysed by a particular viewer. There are divisions in society. Different people come from different background and class conditions. So audience response forms in a very complex and unequal situation.

TV is a form of new media. It is also termed as 'cool media'. Moreover TV is a dominant factor in home life. Thus, in spite of many other new media, TV continues to be a powerful media in the modern society. This is why this research focuses on TV in influencing children's behavior and thoughts.

The functions of TV clear out why audiences watch TV. Firstly, TV creates a household leisure time. It creates a boundary between public and domestic life. Secondly, on the one hand TV brings the world nearer to the viewer and on the other it isolates the viewer from other socialites. Thirdly, TV directs a power play in the home. Member of family who has greater choice over the viewing programmes and who has greater control over the remote is the more powerful one. (Miller2002:104-6). Fourthly, TV opens up a platform of interaction and communication for its viewers. Viewers do not only interact, they also form their perceptions. Fifthly, TV is a cheap, available and colourful medium of providing information and entertainment. It gives us the commonsense knowledge to manage our everyday life. (Ott2007: 1-26). Sixthly, viewers have certain psychological needs. They seek for gratifications of these needs and TV consciously and actively satisfies these needs of the viewers. (Fiske2003: 49-53). Seventhly, TV functions as a companion to the viewers. Eighthly, TV offers a fantasy world. It gives viewers a chance to escape from the boredom and tensions of the real world. Lastly, TV can function as a medium which satisfies the arousal tendencies of the viewers. (Gunter and McAleer1997: 17-26).

It is usually assumed that children are vulnerable to the evils of TV and hence there should

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be regulation codes of the content of TV and its timings. There is no uniform view of how a child should be defined. One view sees child as owned by their parents and thus are controlled by the parents. This view is known as property paradigm. The second view can be termed as protection paradigm as it considers children as someone who need to be protected from all the harmful contents of the society. The third view of children considers them as autonomous individuals with distinct thoughts, behaviors and capacities. Children have the capacity to select and interpret contents for themselves. This view is called personal paradigm. Among these three views, the protection paradigm remains dominant. Usually it is thought that children are vulnerable to media contents and need to be protected. Hence as there is no consensus of how a child should be viewed, there is no consensus of what are the good programmes for children. (Simpson2004: 31-50).

TV is generally accused of many evils. It is even considered as a new source of child abuse. It is argued that TV displaces other activities like playing, attending friends and families, reading, drawing etc. (Gunter1997: 9-14). Secondly, TV focuses on making consumers. It creates desires in young minds which cannot be satisfied every time. (Johnson2000: 200-5). It is inculcating bad habits in the children and also affecting their behavior and thought patterns. Regulation of TV materials is also not out of confusion. The contradictions centres on how to regulate TV contents. Who will regulate? It is assumed that state can take an upper hand in this issue as it is the state's responsibility to safeguard public interest. Apart from looking after the public interest, state should also support the market. For this, it should allow broadcasters to broadcast programmes they prefer. But TV regulation policy is also a part of family policy. Hence, state should be conscious of not infringing rights of families. (Simpson2004: 6-22).

Though irrespective of adult or children, anyone can be influenced and affected by media. It is also correct that children are more prone to be affected by mass media. As children are undergoing

cognitive, intellectual and behavioral developments, they may not be fully aware of the ill-effects of TV. Children have less world experience and less real world knowledge. So, they are usually curious and eager to learn and experience the new and unknown which make them receptive to mass media. These reasons make it significant to discuss the impacts of TV on children. Children are different from each other on the respect of social, physical, psychological and cognitive aspect. Different kinds of children make different kinds of viewers who in turn are differently influenced by the media. (Strasburger2002: 5-29).

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Violence

TV has certain impacts on children. In the following parts, the impacts of TV on children will be analysed. Issues of violence, sexuality and advertising will have a special focus.

TV has been accused of exposing children to a great amount of violence. Though TV cannot be blamed solely in this point, it is also true that there is a significant rise of violent content in the TV than earlier. This makes society worry about the quantity, quality and impact of media violence. (Simpson2004: 94-6). When the term violence is explained, the key term is aggression. The perception of violence is actually the main problem when it comes to the bad impact of TV violence on children. It is very important how one understands the term violence, how he interprets it. This means the construction of violence in society is crucial. (Simpson2004: 97-100). Realism is one important factor which helps in shaping the meaning of violence. Programme which seems to be more real influences perceptions. Familiarity with the surrounding environment also helps in a great deal in building perceptions. (Gunter1997: 95-6). There is no simple and linear analysis to explain why humans have violent dispositions. Media cannot be solely blamed for children's consumption of violence. Individual's

own instincts, habits and psyche, i.e., the type of viewer is also responsible for any consumption of violence.(Strasburger2002: 73-5).To some extent aggressive behavior is normal in children. These are called normative aggressive behaviour. What makes the researchers worry is the individual difference of aggressive behaviour in children. Both nature and nurture are responsible for this individual variation.(Kirsch2006:21-31). It is also true that every kind of media, be it internet, TV, video games or any other, is full with violent and aggressive contents. (Miller2002:11-2). An obvious question then crop up that why children consume violent material at all? First, children have imitative tendencies. Secondly, violence that is morally defensible or violence that is rewarded draws more attention from the children. Thirdly, realistic violence can shock children. But unrealistic violence or violence with humour and fun draws attention from children. For instance, though cartoon contains violence, children love watching them because the seriousness of violence is minimized in cartoon programme.(Strasburger2002:95-100). So, the problem of media violence is not actually in broadcasting them, but in not showing details, i.e., the consequence and nature of violence is not truly represented. Fourthly, children have a need of companionship. So when they are in groups, they often watch violence to be a part of a group who treats violence as cool or heroic. Fifthly, children consume violent media just to pass time and to relax. Sixthly, some children get more aroused from violence and they consume violent media out of habit and addiction. Seventhly, children are mostly taught to behave polite in schools and from parents. When they watch violence they have a forbidden fruit pleasure of 'doing' violence. Eighthly, on the one hand society teaches children to be non-violent. On the other it also gives an impression that violence is daring and brave which also can be a solution to many problems. Violent acts of self-defence and also defence of country or one's family is socially approved.(Kirsch2006:79-90).The notable effects of TV violence on children are: first, prolonged exposure to TV violence produces a 'mean world

syndrome' in the minds of the children. They can have nightmares and other behavioural disorders due to this fright. (Miller2002:13).Ninthly, researchers have warned that TV violence can make children non-responsive to violence, i.e., it can desensitize children.(Gunter1997:100).Legitimizing and sanitizing violence in real life is very dangerous and disturbing. To avoid this, portrayals of violence need to be treated with care and over-exposure of violence should be avoided in all sense. (Simpson2004:119-21).Finally, usually children are prone to imitate and hence children have this tendency to imitate violent acts. Some children are more aroused by TV violence and they imitate more. (Gunter1997:97-9).However, TV violence can also have some good effects on children. They are: 1) Portrayals of consequences of violence can teach children about the risks and problems of violence.2), A clear and fair idea of violence can help children to deal maturely with anxieties and fear.(Kirsch2006:100-11).

Sexuality

By sexuality we understand both the physical and mental traits and also of a social identity. The basic concept of masculinity^{xi} and feminism^{xii} comes from the concept of sexuality only. It is thought that the contents of TV programmes are sexually suggestive and irresponsible. Movies, soap serials and advertisements are showing sexually explicit contents and images in prime time. (Strasburger2002:145-6).Concept of sexuality is never free from the idea of morality, and it is assumed media affects individual's sense of moral obligations. (Tester1994:81-100).With digital era coming, people's right to privacy and newer sexual representations are coming up with continuously evolved meanings. (Arthurs2004:1-3).Tastes and moral attitudes of the audiences keep changing from time to time. So, broadcasters cannot aim for all kinds of audiences in one program. Here is when creating a genre is significant. The assumed genre will be consumed by audiences with similar tastes, choices and ideas of pleasure. Audiences are being

more receptive to sexual content than they were previously. But when TV is broadcasting any program, it needs to take care of censorship. TV needs to maintain certain codes on sex and nudity. Censorship is done in the belief to protect viewers, especially the child viewers from harmful unsuitable contents. But with the rise of sexual citizenship^{xiii} a growing demand is being posed on sexual consumerism. With this the regulation and censorship are reducing and being more lenient. (Arthurs2004:5-37). Advertisers and producers have come to agree to the fact that 'sex sells'. With this they seem to be reluctant to address the threats and problems that 'sex' can bring. On the contrary issues like adolescent sexuality, premarital sex, teen pregnancy, rape and even prostitution are glamorized in many instances. (Strasburger2002:145-7). In the modern era, audiences are being offered a variety of programs and audiences too have their own preferences, choices and thoughts. Audiences also have their distinct reactions to any program. All these have made pornography to come into mainstream culture and as well as in prime time programs. A certain pornochic^{xiv} culture is growing fast. (Arthur2004:38-43). With more liberal attitudes towards sexuality it is getting really difficult to control children from exposure to sexualities in an early age. Moreover children are not only exposed to all these contents from other media along with TV, the contents can be easily recorded and can provide repeated shows. (Simpson2004:126-30). Now the question is: why are children more susceptible to media sexualities? Children often relate themselves with the TV actors and want to imitate them. So there is a risk that with imitating program having irresponsible sexualities, children may develop a wrong sexual behaviour and morality. Moreover, children take the screen world for real many a times. (Strasburger2002:157-60). I will turn to summarise the effects of media sexuality on children. Firstly, TV being an audiovisual help makes the portrayals look attractive and real. These portrayals seem to be retained in a child's mind and become more dangerous if the child tries them out

in an age unsuitable for the behavior. Secondly, TV can influence children's attitudes and ideologies. Children can develop to believe in a stereotypical sex role. Not only that, children may develop a wrong perspective about gender, beauty and the role of women. Thirdly, programs containing media sexualities are often more focused on commercial benefits rather than providing education. These programs do not warn the viewers about the threats of sexual acts. For example, threats of premarital sex and pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases mostly go unnoticed. (Strasburger2002:150-7). Hence there are attempts to control and censor sexual contents. It is suggested that contents must be responsible to portray images that are true and normal. Moreover programs should not cross the limits of decency and public order. The sanctity of culture must be maintained. (Sinclair2004:10-11). But all these concepts and terms are vague. Subjective meanings underlie the concepts. For instance terms like 'normal', 'decent', 'responsible' etc have varied meanings to every individual. So, it can be said that vagueness in concepts and lack of clarification make it difficult to develop normative regulations. (Simpson2004:131-46). Media sexualities also have some pro-social^{xv} and developmental roles and this cannot be denied.

TV can play a role of an informer and a peer. (Strasburger2002:147-9). Secondly, though not every time but many a times the risks and threats of sexual activities are portrayed. For instance, messages on family planning, contraceptive advertisements, programs and promotion on prevention of AIDS, safe sex and other health messages warn children about the risks of sexualities. (Strasburger2002:178-187). The question is: How can media sexualities have healthier and developmental effects on children? Some solutions can be offered. Media sexualities should carry a moral obligation to address the risks of sexualities. Advertisements should have a taste in decency and should remember that they too have a public health responsibility. Media sexualities should take the role of being a sex-educator. (Strasburger2002:192-4).

Advertising

Advertising (hereafter will be referred as Ads) is the third aspect of any media, especially TV, which have a major impact on children. Now a major part of TV schedule is filled up with Advertising. Children are an important 'market'. The ad industry considers children as very profitable consumers. Like regulating violence and sexuality, regulating ads are not easy. The 'innocent child' view suggests that children are under cognitive development and thus they cannot understand the purpose of ads. This is why they are susceptible to all kinds of negative influences an ad can have. So, ads are to be strictly regulated from children. But the 'autonomous child' view opposes this perspective by saying that if ads have negative influences, then adults are also the victims of such influences. Hence there is no point in regulating ads from children. So, regulating ads are not an easy decision to be taken. But usually different countries are in a consensus that ads should not encourage in promoting unsafe or illegal products; should avoid images frightening and provocative; should not misguide and misinform. Regulating the duration of ads in a program is also a matter of concern. (Simpson2004:149-60). Though viewers are not passive, advertisers are indirect actors who indirectly construct the choices of the consumers. Advertisers are more concerned about the audiences than their advertised products. (Bel2005:199-206). So it is very important for the viewers to understand the intention of the ads and as well as the advertisers which is not an easy task. At this point a genuine concern arrives that how far children are capable of understanding the aim of an ad? Children are not attentive to every ad. Some features like the jingles, slogans or fun elements of ads draw children's attention. As children grow up, they mostly understand the selling purpose of ads. They can also understand that ads do not tell the truth always. (Gunter1997:126-37). Ads are used to convince audience in buying. Usually ads target the urban audience more. A capitalist's view and upper-middle class lifestyle is shown as desirable and dominant through the ads. So it is clear that ads are

very commercial in nature and always target for a profitable consumer. Researches mostly found that children are influenced by ads. (Chauhan2001:195-235). But why are children especially attentive towards ads? As children face a problem in differentiating real and fiction, they have a tendency to trust the ads more than adults. Secondly, whatever appears bright, colourful, tasty in ads attract children. So it is easier for ads to catch the attention of a child viewer. Thirdly, children are mostly persistent about their needs. They want whatever appeals them and insist their parents to buy them what they have seen in ads. Fourthly, children are not matured enough to understand the symbolic and hidden message of the ads. Fifthly, children these days have greater amount of pocket money. So they are more independent to buy and spend. (Strasburger2002:35-60). This also makes clear about the reason why children are the most affected by ads. There are some kinds of ads that are more frequent, prominent and dominant than others, such as food ads. Food ads often offer toys to appeal children. For instance McDonalds offer toys with their happy meals. Health drinks like Horlicks or Complan offer pencil box sets or flying discs. Children are more carried away with all these free gifts and colourful food ads. They are not much concerned with the nutritional values of the foods advertised. Cartoon characters play an additional role to increase the popularity of certain food products. (Strasburger2002:237-47). The effects of ads on children are many and are intense in nature.

The Child as Consumer

Children are flattered with choice and this develops a keen desire to consume more and more. Secondly, though children have pocket money, but they cannot buy everything they see in ads whenever they want. Thirdly, children take ads for real. (Strasburger2002:53-7). Fourthly, Ads always show people consuming high calorie sugared foods but rarely show them over-weight. Punch lines like 'no one can eat just one' in Lays encourage a snacking behaviour in children. This not only serves poor nutritional knowledge but also promotes a

poor diet habit in children. (Gunter1997:147-50).Obesityxviiican bring health problems like hypertension, lipid disorders, heart problems, diabetes, orthopaedic problems, blood pressure problems, thyroid, respiratory problem and many more. Dental problems also occur due to wrong food habits. (Strasburger2002: 251-6).Fifthly, in the make-belief world created by ads being slim and beautiful becomes very important.(Strasburger2002:265-6).Sixthly, with drug ads and alcohol ads getting mainstreamed, ads promote that drinking is social and desirable. There are many social problems that come from drinking and smoking like health problems, strain relationships, unhealthy family environment, involvement in crime, violence and sexuality, social criticisms, accidents etc. smoking is one of the main causes of death and fatal diseases like cancer. But ads rarely show the dangers that are probable from drinking and smoking.(Gunter1997:150).Seventhly,Children are exposed to a variety of issues from a very early age. This does not only affect the moralities of children, but also make them grow too fast. (Miller2002:74-8).Lastly, ads shape the mentalities of children in a very wrong way. Ads affect the value system, moral standards, cognition and thinking of children in a wrong way.(Chauhan2001:229-33).

Concluding Remarks

It is not possible to ban TV from a child's life now. Since the last 10-15 year TV has changed and developed in a manner that is unprecedented in the history of the media. It has become a necessary part of our life which cannot be escaped from. Moreover neither is the case that TV only has negative effects nor is it the case that children are always interested in programs. It is also to be noted that children can learn from all kinds of programmes. So, care should be taken to make informational and educational programs to be interesting. The State, parents and school have a responsibility to teach children being a prudent user of TV.(Gunter1997:208-13).Most of the regulatory codes of TV try to protect children from harmful media contents.. A new concept of 'child-citizen' has come up in which children are thought of

as autonomous and independent being. Children are growing up to adulthood. So if they do not learn to face situations from now, how can they grow up into a matured citizen? So regulation is not easy. A balance should be made between the children's right and adult's right. The State also needs to strike a balance between regulating content according public health and also seeing the economic profits of broadcasters.(Simpson2004:166-80).Parents cannot always monitor their children. Instead parents need to make children sensible enough to protect themselves. To do this two things are important. Firstly, we should do a detailed audience research, especially child-audience research. This will help to know the psychological makeup of a child, more as a viewer. Secondly, parents are needed to be mobilized. Parents should also encourage children in involving themselves in other creative activities. (Oswell1999:66-87).In the new democratic modern world, media and its information are important. Participating in the media and consuming it are also important. Children and their parents need to be better informed about world, society, media and its persuasive intention. This means that one needs to be media literateix.One should understand that no media is completely good or bad. Parents should co-view TV program with their children. This may lead them to discuss the issues in a program with their children, initiate interaction among the family members and also helps parents in monitoring the quality and quantity of programs watched by their children. Parents should also encourage children to engaging themselves in other activities like playing and reading. Parents should join their children in all these activities.TV in bedroom should be avoided. Using TV as a babysitter should also be strictly avoided.(Strasburger2002:322-67). Hence an awareness of media and its effects from the part of parents and children can protect children from the harmful impacts of TV. (Strasburger2002:322-67).

ⁱ The term technology derives from the original Greek word 'tekhne' meaning art or skill. According to Collins English Dictionary (1979), technology is the application of practical or mechanical sciences to industry or commerce; the methods, theory and practices governing such application; the total knowledge and skills available to any human society for industry, art, science etc. – See Grint and Woolgar, 1997. Technologies have always assisted communications. It includes printing press and other means of recording text and images. Technologies help to allow rapid communication over great distances. These technologies are commonly called Media Technologies. --- See Lax, 2009.

ⁱⁱ Contents that are involved in a dialogue pattern are called dialogic. They intend to get some sort of response and reaction from the audience. – See Tester, 1994.

ⁱⁱⁱ Differences and diversities of interpretations are called polysemy. – See Tester.

^{iv} Culture is derived from the term agriculture which means to cultivate. Culture is a totality of life that is cultivated over a period of time. It is a complex whole of values. – See Chandra, 2000.

^v New media are media with technology to present their services and which can reach out to a wider audience. Hence they are cheap in availability and have easy storage options. They are also easy to read. New media are available for 24x7 hours and are platform of business along with being platform for sharing information. –See Razdan, 2008.

^{vi} Media which offer high levels of participation are called cool media. –See Fiske.

^{vii} Any human being under the age of 18 years is legally defined as children. Sometimes 21 years continues to be the upper age limit of childhood. Children are considered young beings who have not attended puberty and hence they are considered as immature person. For this reason government have the responsibility to protect the rights of children in a society. Children are human beings different from adults.

^{viii} Violence can be defined as force whether covert or overt, used to wrest from an individual something that he does not want to give of his own free will and which causes her either physical injury or emotional trauma or both. Violence can take many forms like criminal violence (rape, abduction, and murder), domestic violence (dowry deaths,

sexual abuse, maltreatment) or social violence (eve-teasing, harassments). –See Ahuja, 2006.

^{ix} Aggression is a form of violence which is very physical and not justified. But some form of defensive aggression is necessary to survive. –See Simpson.

^x A syndrome which provokes one to think and believe that the world is a mean and dangerous place. –See Chandra, 2000.

^{xi} Various socially constructed collections of assumptions, expectations and ways of behaving the serve as standards for forms of male behavior. See Bilton, 1997.

^{xii} Various socially constructed collections of assumptions, expectations and ways of behaving the serve as standards for female behavior. –See Bilton.

^{xiii} Sexual citizens are the sexual consumers. The taste and choice of these consumers are influenced by their sexual identities. – See Arthurs, 2004

^{xiv} Pornochic is the representation of pornography in non-pornographic art and culture. It is the modern transformation of pornography into mainstream culture. – See Arthurs, 2004.

^{xv} Beliefs, elements, thoughts and actions that conform to the social norms are called pro-social. Pro-social behavior helps in the development of social regulations. It also helps to maintain the societal norms and is believed to maintain social solidarity as well.

^{xvi} Karl Marx has discussed the concept of Capitalism in his book *Capital*. He describes capitalism as a system of commodity production. Capitalism involves a nation-wide and often an international, exchange market. Every commodity has use value and exchange value. In contrast to use value, exchange value presupposes a definite economic relation and is inseparable from a market on which goods are exchanged. It has meaning in reference to commodity. The main principle of capitalism is to make profit. –See Giddens, 1996.

^{xvii} A hidden message is such an information which is not manifested openly and thus audience fail to notice and interpret the real meaning of the message. A hidden message is to be interpreted to know the real meaning. Hidden message can take many forms.

^{xviii} Being obese is defined as having a body mass index, or BMI – a measurement of body fat of 30 or greater. Obesity can lead to heart disease, stroke, high blood pressure, diabetes and even some forms of cancer. The number of obese person is growing in

the modern world. Marketers push fast food and other high-energy, high-fat processed foods. These foods help in storing fat. – See Food Cures, Readers Digest. 2010.

^{xix} Media literacy is a repertoire of competences that enable people to analyse, evaluate and create messages in a wide variety of media modes, genres and forms. Education for media literacy often uses a inquiry based pedagogic model that encourages people to ask questions about what they watch, hear and read. It provides loads of tools to help people critically analyse messages, offers opportunities for learners to broaden their experience of media and helps them to develop creative skills in making their own media messages. – See http://www.cineliteracy.com/modules/wfchannel/admin/index.php?op=editandwfc_cid=1

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